

CERTIFICATION OF ENROLLMENT

Study title: Multicentered Prospective Randomized Controlled Trial On Contrast-Enhanced Harmonic Endoscopic Ultrasound (CH_EUS) Vs Conventional EUS-Guided Fine Needle Biopsy (FNB) For Solid Pancreatic Lesions

IRRB number: IRRB/32/21

(hereinafter referred to as “Study”)

Promoter: The Chinese University of Hong Kong

(Hereinafter referred to as “Promoter”)

The Promoter of the Study here certifies that the Centre IRCCS ISMETT has enrolled in total N° 83 patients, of which N° 43 in 2023.

Date: 5 March, 2024

Name: Raymond Shing-Yan Tang

Signature on behalf of the Promoter:

Position/Title: Assistant Professor, Department of Medicine and Therapeutics, The Chinese University of Hong Kong